

THE ROLE OF COMPARATIVE METHODOLOGY IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING

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Abstract:

This article talks about the methodology of foreign language teaching, the history of its development as a science, the types of modern methods used in the methodology of foreign language teaching and their use.

Key words: methodology, innovation, foreign language, communication, skill, qualification, didactics

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Today's informative progress has given rise to a new way of advanced pedagogy. Ground-breaking means "summary (dissemination) of modernization" in English. The socio-psychological feature of novelty was established by the American researcher E. Rogers. He intentional the organization of the participants of the innovation procedure, their defiance to the origination, etc. The concepts of originality and modernization are equally changed in scientific guidelines. "Innovation" means an instrument, new system, methodology, technology. "Innovation" is a development that matures affording to convinced periods of education. World scientific expansion is growing and emerging daily. It was this positive progress that had an impact on our nation. Advanced innovative technologies are being functional to our world of skill. As a result of this, our President named this year as the "the Year of Support for Youth and Business", which increased the responsibility of the youth of our country. It would not be wrong to say that the wide request of advanced, contemporary innovative technologies in the arenas of education has opened the door to countless prospects and goals for young people learning foreign languages. Language learning is one of the most important areas in human society. Language, which is a means of communication, can be acquired practically in a natural environment, i.e. in the family, among the public or in an organized manner. Knowledge of language wonders is taught supposedly. Knowledge of languages, exclusively multilingualism, is of great position in our time when intercontinental relations are on the increase. Followers and students learning in our country usually study three languages. These languages are denoted to by special names. These are: mother tongue, second language, and foreign language. The mother tongue is the first language that plays a special role in the development of intelligent. When talking about the second language, it is measured as the language of relatives and neighbors who are representatives of other nations.

A foreign language is the language which enters from abroad. Western European languages (English, Spanish, German, French) and Eastern languages

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(Arabic, Turkish, Persian, Chinese, Indian) are taught in our republic. These languages are counted in in the programs of educational institutions. The process of teaching all three languages is diverse. The mother tongue and the second language are learned in a natural situation, and a foreign language is learned in an artificial environment. Communication in a foreign language mainly takes place in the classroom under the mentoring of the teacher. Among the three languages, learning and teaching a foreign language differs gradually in certain features. This, in turn, involves the use of suitable foreign language teaching expertise. By carefully grasping the accomplishments of the methodical skill, the foreign language teacher will be able to obviously know the standard of language experience of the student and to improve it further. Actual teaching of foreign languages requires knowledge of its methodology. Learning and teaching foreign languages mainly hang on on the hypothetical development of foreign language teaching methodology matters and the original application of theory in practice. The main concepts of methodology - method, method, principle. Didactics - what do we teach? is the content of education. Methodology - how do we teach? means educational methods and methods. Method - the concept of methodology is derived from the Greek-Latin word "methodos-"methodus" and means the means of ways and methods leading to a certain goal. In various literature, you can find the narrow and broad meaning of the term. The term "methodology" in a narrow sense means the idea connected to the real lesson progression of education. It is understood as a directed learning process that includes instruction related to lesson planning and preparation of teaching materials. The term "method" in a broad sense refers to the selection, classification and distribution of educational material. "Didactics" and "methodology" have been used in the narrow sense in the Federal Republic of Germany since the 1960s. Accordingly, what is the content of didactic education taught? How are teaching methods taught? He deals with his issues. Learning foreign languages is not only a means of intellectual education, but also a process of personality formation by getting to know the educational resources and values of a foreign culture and applying them to one's own cultural life. In Europe, the study of foreign languages has long been considered a privilege in higher education, and public schools have been seen as educating the privileged few. The method of teaching a foreign language means the set of activities of the teacher and the student that ensures the achievement of the practical, general educational, educational and developmental goals of teaching a foreign language. The term "method" is used in the sense of "set of educational methods" and "direction of education". First, in the theory of education, the process is used in the sense of methods, and in the second sense, we can find it in works on the history of teaching methods. For example, translation method, correct method, conscious-comparative method, traditional method, intensive method, etc. are considered as foreign language teaching methods. The most important of the principles is to create a language environment. Various approaches have appeared in the practical application of the advanced methodical principles. This can be clearly seen in the creative activity of the method exponents. The new interpretation of the goal of foreign language education was mainly based on the results of pragmatic linguistics research. This field of linguistics interprets language as a field of human activity rather than a system of linguistic forms. A set of new conclusions, which began to be collected in the field of foreign language education since the beginning of the 70s, led to intense discussions in the field of setting educational goals. The new curricula, which define the main

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directions of foreign language education, have been adopted, the purpose of which is to "teach students how to behave". In the 70s, the "communicative method" was proven in several stages after a series of attempts. In this way, the science of methodology was developing. We cannot master any foreign language without studying its methodology in depth. The method of "communicative didactics" is also considered important in the methodology of foreign language teaching. Communicative didactics includes the following. Learning a foreign language is a multifaceted teaching, and in this process a person experiences complex psychological change. In particular, the process of comparing the native language with a foreign language occurs. Various teaching methods and technologies are used in this process. With the help of modern pedagogical technologies, teaching by comparing a foreign language with the mother tongue gives an effective result. Teaching a foreign language requires knowledge of its methodology. Methodology and technologies are important in the process of learning a foreign language. There are various methods of teaching methodology. The widely used methods in foreign language teaching methodology are: communicative didactic method, intercultural dialogue organization method and exercise organization method. Since the science of methodology is related to the science of didactics, it is based on communicativeness during foreign language learning and the method of communicative didactics is created.

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